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Remarks on *Parornix ampliatelylla* (STANTON, 1850) (Lepidoptera: Gracillariidae)

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Abstract: On the basis of reared specimens from Croatia, a brief description of morphology and life history of *Parornix ampliatelylla* (STANTON) is given. The larval host plant was *Prunus mahaleb* L. Detailed morphological descriptions of the adults and their genitalia are provided to facilitate accurate species identification.

Key words: *Parornix ampliatelylla*, Gracillariidae, morphology, life history, *Prunus mahaleb*.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Parornix* SPULER, 1910 is represented by 75 species distributed in the temperate climate zone of the northern hemisphere (GRACILLARIIDAE.NET 2025). The moths are very uniform as concerns their external appearance, and therefore their identification usually requires rearing from the larvae or dissection of the genitalia. However, unlike the external appearance, the genitalia are quite diverse, and this was the reason for establishing several subgenera (KUZNETZOV 1976).

Visiting Croatia in October 2003, I collected on *Prunus mahaleb* L. a number of larvae whose feeding pattern clearly indicated that they belonged to the genus *Parornix* SPUL. Further rearing and genitalia dissection confirmed the species as *Parornix ampliatelylla* (STANTON). This species has a rather limited distribution in the central part of Mediterranean area and Central Europe. It was described from Croatia (STANTON 1850), and later it was also recorded from Italy, France (Corsica) and Austria (DE PRINS & DE PRINS 2005, GRACILLARIIDAE.NET 2025).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The investigated material includes 34 specimens reared from larvae and two adult specimens collected during the day:

Croatia, Podgora, 7♂♂, 5♀♀, e.l. 26.01-21.03.2004, J. Buszko leg.; larvae 12.10.2003 on *Prunus mahaleb*.

Croatia, Makarska, 9♂♂, 13♀♀, e.l. 25.01-21.03.2004, J. Buszko leg.; larvae 13.10.2003 on *Prunus mahaleb*.

Croatia, Makarska, 2♂, 22.04.2004, flushed during the day from shrubby vegetation, J. Buszko leg.

At the above mentioned localities, tenanted larval shelters were collected, which were subsequently kept in plastic containers filled with leaves and folded paper. The larvae made their cocoons in the folds of paper. To simulate natural overwintering conditions, the breeding containers were kept outdoors. Hatched moths were spread following generally accepted methods for Microlepidoptera. The specimens are stored in author's collection. Photos of set adults were taken using a Leica stereomicroscope with a mounted digital camera and focus bracketing application.

Morphology

Adult (Figs. 1, 2). Wingspan 10.2-11.7 mm (n = 36). Sex dimorphism indistinct. Head: frons, maxillar and labial palpus entirely white. Vertex covered with white, hair-like scales admixed with two small bunches of dark grey scales above scapus. Antenna dark grey with a narrow yellowish annulation. Thorax white, with two small lateral dark spots on the back. Tegulae at the base covered with scattered dark scales. Sometimes the dark scale cover extends to the fore part of thorax. Legs: coxa and femur of the fore and mid leg blackish speckled with white. Tarsus white with distal part of tarsomeres ringed blackish. Hind leg brownish grey, distal ends of tarsomeres marked with dark grey. Spurs white. Wings: fore wing with typical pattern for *Parornix* species. Ground color in the basal area pure white changing to dark grey toward the apex. Costa with numerous white strigulae. Two large blackish spots in dorsal part of the wing. Another dark spot at the end of median cell. Black apical dot bordered inwardly by a white strigula. Cilia white with three blackish lines. Two outer cilia lines distinct and complete, the basal line less prominent and interrupted below the apical dot. Hind wing greyish-brown with cilia of the same color. Abdomen greyish-brown.

Figs. 1–2. 1. ♂, *Parornix ampliata* (STT.), Croatia, Makarska, e.l. 15.03.2004, J. Buszko leg.; 2. ♀ *Parornix ampliata* (STT.), Croatia, Makarska, e.l. 25.01.2004, J. Buszko leg. (photos M. Stachowiak).

Genitalia. The genitalia of both sexes are illustrated in the atlas of French Lepidoptera (NEL & VARENE 2015), and male genitalia in lateral view in Russian key (KUZNETZOV, 1981). Here, the illustrations are supplemented with descriptions.

Male genitalia (Figs. 3–5): tegumen short, its upper part slightly elongated and followed with a long and narrow tuba analis. Vinculum extends ventrally in a short and slender saccus.

Figs. 3–6. Genitalia of *Parornix ampliata* (STT.): 3 – male genitalia, 4 – aedeagus, 5 – ventral plate, 6 – female genitalia (orig.).

Anellus without lateral projections. Valvae asymmetrical, oval in outline, their apical part slightly widened. Left valva broader with clearly developed lobe near the basis. Outer margins of valvae densely covered with bristles. Ventral plate of the 8th segment rather long with rounded apex. Aedeagus with a short broad coecum and two long curved lateral branches. Branches are widened at the tips and covered with numerous short spines.

Female genitalia (Fig. 6): papillae anales wide. Apophyses posteriores short, thin, bent in half its length. Apophyses anteriores short, spine-like. Antrum sclerotized, ostium bursae diagonal. Ductus bursae membranous, medium width, slightly widened anteriorly. Ductus

seminalis joints ductus bursae just below antrum. Corpus bursae elliptical, approximately 2/5 length of ductus bursae, inside with two bands of corn-shaped sclerites, which are larger in the central part of the band.

Life history

The larval host plant of *P. ampliarella* is *Prunus mahaleb* L. Eggs are laid on the underside of the leaf. During its first instars, larva lives internally making a small blotch mine (Figs. 7, 8). The larva initially mines in the lower epidermis making a whitish opaque mine. Most likely, mines of this species were discovered by Klimesch, but he determined them as belonging to *Parornix anguliferella* (ZELL.) (KLIMESCH 1942). After the third moult, the larva leaves the mine and lives externally, folding a leaf along the main vein, spinning the edges and creating a pod-like shelter (Figs. 9, 10). Then it consumes the leaf content except outer epidermis, usually starting from tip of the leaf. Full grown larva abandons the shelter, descends to the ground and makes a brownish cocoon in the leaf litter. The presence of larvae in autumn and an adult in spring suggests that this species has at least two generations per year. The preferred habitat is sunny slopes on limestone rocks with the presence of a host plant. Traces of feeding were also found in gardens and urban green areas.

Figs. 7–10. Mines and feeding traces of *Parornix ampliarella* (STT.): 7, 8 – mines, 9, 10 – feeding traces (photos J. Buszko).

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